

Git-Database Branch Integration with DDL Versioning and Webhook Automation

Daniel Moya
daniel.moya@dimensigon.com
Dimensigon

27 March 2026

Publication Type: Defensive Publication – Prior Art Disclosure

Classification: cs.DB (Databases)

License: CC-BY-4.0

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19244217

Abstract

We present a deep integration between Git version control and database branching, comprising six sub-systems: (1) LinkManager for bidirectional Git-branch to DB-branch mapping, (2) CommitTracker for recording database state at Git commits, (3) DdlVersioning for automatic WAL-based DDL capture with schema snapshots, (4) DiffEngine for schema and data comparison between branches at arbitrary LSN/SCN points, (5) HookManager for Git hooks (post-checkout, pre-commit, post-merge) that auto-switch database branches, and (6) WebhookServer for GitHub/GitLab PR lifecycle automation. The DiffEngine supports three levels: schema-only (<100ms), schema plus sampled data (1-5s), and full data diff (scales with data size). Diff targets include branch current state, branch-at-LSN, and branch-at-SCN, enabling cross-branch time-travel comparisons. No existing database links Git branches to database branches with automatic DDL capture from WAL monitoring and PR webhook automation.

Keywords: Git Integration, Database Branching, DDL Versioning, Schema Diff, Git Hooks, Webhooks, Database-as-Code, Time-Travel Diff

1 1. Background and Prior Art

Flyway/Liquibase: Schema migration tools using numbered migration scripts. No Git branch linking, no automatic DDL capture, no database branching, no diff engine.

Dolt: Git-like database with native branch/merge/diff. However, Dolt IS the repository – it does not integrate with an external Git repository. No PR webhook automation linking Git and database lifecycles.

Atlas (Ariga): Schema-as-code with CI integration. Generates migration plans from desired schema state. No embedded database, no runtime Git-DB branch linking, no WAL-based DDL capture.

PlanetScale: Deploy requests are similar to PRs for schema changes. No Git repository integration, no DDL capture from WAL, no automatic branch linking on checkout.

Prisma Migrate: Schema migration from Prisma schema files. Client-side tool, not database-integrated.

2 2. Technical Contribution

2.1 2.1 LinkManager: Bidirectional Branch Mapping

RocksDB key-value storage for Git-to-DB branch mappings:

```

1 git:link:{git_branch_name} -> BranchId (database branch UUID)
2 git:config -> GitConfig { repo_path, auto_create_branches, default_branch }

```

On `git checkout feature-x`, the post-checkout hook calls LinkManager to resolve the database branch and switch the active connection context. If no mapping exists and `auto_create_branches` is enabled, a new database branch is created from the current main branch.

2.2 2.2 CommitTracker: State Recording at Git Commits

```

1 git:commit:{commit_hash} -> CommitState { branch_id, lsn, scn, schema_hash, timestamp }
2 git:schema_snapshot:{commit_hash} -> SerializedSchema { tables, columns, indexes, constraints }

```

At each Git commit, CommitTracker records the database LSN, SCN, and a hash of the current schema. This enables restoring database state to any Git commit point without replaying migration scripts.

2.3 2.3 DdlVersioning: WAL-Based DDL Capture

The DdlVersioning module monitors the write-ahead log for DDL statements (CREATE TABLE, ALTER TABLE, DROP TABLE, CREATE INDEX, etc.) and records them with timestamps:

```

1 git:ddl:{timestamp}:{sequence} -> DdlEntry { sql, lsn, branch_id, tables_affected }

```

This provides an automatic, complete history of all schema changes without requiring developers to write migration files. The DDL history integrates with Git commit state for schema-at-commit reconstruction.

2.4 2.4 DiffEngine: Multi-Level Branch Comparison

Three diff target types enable flexible comparison:

```

1 enum DiffTarget {
2     Branch(String), // current state
3     BranchAtLsn { branch: String, lsn: u64 }, // specific transaction
4     BranchAtScn { branch: String, scn: u64 }, // system change number
5 }

```

Schema diff compares table definitions, column types, indexes, and constraints. Data diff uses SQL EXCEPT/INTERSECT for row-level comparison with configurable sampling rates.

2.5 2.5 Git Hooks

- **post-checkout**: Auto-switch active database branch to match Git branch
- **pre-commit**: Validate schema consistency (no uncommitted DDL conflicts)
- **post-merge**: Reconcile database branch after Git merge, detect schema conflicts

2.6 2.6 WebhookServer: PR Lifecycle Automation

Handles GitHub/GitLab webhook events to automate database branch lifecycle:

Event	Action
PR opened	Create database branch from base branch
PR push/update	Apply pending schema changes to DB branch
PR merged	Merge database branch into target
PR closed (not merged)	Delete database branch

```

1 git:pr:{pr_number} -> PrState { db_branch_id, base_branch, status, created_at }

```

3 3. Implementation

Implemented in Rust as part of HeliosDB Nano (AGPL-3.0). Module: `git_integration/` with sub-modules: `config.rs`, `link_manager.rs`, `commit_tracker.rs`, `ddl_versioning/` (WAL capture + schema snapshots), `diff/` (DiffTarget, schema diff, data diff), `hooks/` (post-checkout, pre-commit, post-merge), `webhooks/` (GitHub + GitLab handlers). Total: 385+ LOC in `mod.rs` plus sub-modules.